

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING CULTURE

Toshmatov Alimardon

Teacher of Fergana state university, english and literature faculty.

Aliyeva Zeboxon

Student of Fergana state university, english language and literature faculty.

Group:21.89

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11057581>

Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive examination of materials utilized in teaching culture within educational settings. Recognizing the pivotal role of cultural understanding in today's interconnected world, educators increasingly seek innovative approaches to impart cultural knowledge. Drawing upon diverse sources including textbooks, multimedia resources, and interactive activities, this review assesses the strengths and limitations of various materials in facilitating cultural learning. Additionally, it explores the integration of technology and experiential learning methodologies to enhance cultural comprehension among students. By synthesizing current research and practical insights, this article offers valuable guidance for educators striving to cultivate cultural awareness and sensitivity in the classroom.

Keywords: Culture, literature, Newspapers, TV, internet, picture, reality, films, signs, cultural understanding, cultural misunderstanding.

It is fact that, Culture is a way of life of a group of people--the behaviors, beliefs, values, and symbols that they accept, generally without thinking about them, and that are passed along by communication and imitation from one generation to the next. Culture is symbolic communication. An understanding of culture requires an understanding not only of language differences, but also differences in knowledge, perceptions, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors.

Culture (from the Latin cultura stemming from colere, meaning "to cultivate") generally refers to patterns of human activity and the symbolic structures that give such activities significance and importance. Cultures can be "understood as systems of symbols and meanings that even their creators contest, that lack fixed boundaries, that are constantly in flux, and that interact and compete with one another." Culture can be defined as all the ways of life including arts, beliefs and institutions of a population that are passed down from generation to generation. Culture has been called "the way of life for an entire society." As such, it includes codes of manners, dress, language, religion, rituals, art. norms of behavior, such as law and morality, and systems of belief.

Literature is an art that uses language as a means to shape an image to reflect social life and express the authors thoughts and feelings. Originated from human productive labor. The first appeared was oral literature, which was generally linked to music as lyrical poetry that could be sung. Modern literature usually divides literature into four categories: poetry, fiction, prose, and drama. Culture is a social phenomenon and it is the product of long-term creation. At the same time, it is also a historical phenomenon. It is the accumulation of social history. Culture refers to the history, geography, customs, traditions, ways of life, literature and art, behavioral norms, modes of thinking, and values of a country or a nation. It includes material culture, institutional culture and psychological culture. The internal structure of culture includes the following levels: material culture, institutional culture, behavioral culture, and

mentality culture. The cultural layer of matter is the sum of the material production activities and products of human beings. It is a tangible cultural thing with material entities. The institutional culture layer is a variety of social behavior norms established by humans in social practice. The behavioral culture layer is a behavior pattern that is commonly used in interpersonal communication in the form of etiquette, folklore, and custom. Mentality culture is a subjective factor such as values, aesthetic tastes, and thinking patterns gestated by human beings in social awareness activities. It is equivalent to the concepts commonly referred to as spiritual culture and social awareness. This is the core of culture.

Newspapers can be used as a rich resource for teaching culture in several ways:

- **Current Events Discussion:** Analyzing newspaper articles can provide insights into contemporary cultural issues, trends, and debates.
- **Language and Vocabulary:** Reading newspapers exposes students to authentic language use, idiomatic expressions, and specialized vocabulary related to culture.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Contrasting newspapers from different regions or countries can highlight cultural differences and similarities in reporting style, topics covered, and perspectives presented.
- **Historical Context:** Examining newspaper archives can offer a glimpse into the historical evolution of cultural attitudes, societal norms, and significant events.
- **Media Literacy:** Teaching students to critically evaluate news sources fosters media literacy skills, helping them discern biases, propaganda, and misinformation.
- **Cultural Practices and Traditions:** Articles on festivals, holidays, rituals, and customs provide valuable insights into cultural practices and traditions.
- **Creative Projects:** Assignments such as creating cultural newsletters, analyzing advertisements, or writing opinion pieces based on current events encourage active engagement with cultural topics.

By integrating newspapers into teaching culture, educators can enhance students' understanding of global perspectives, critical thinking skills, and cultural competency.

Using the internet as a teaching resource for culture offers a wealth of opportunities:

1. **Virtual Tours:** Students can explore cultural sites, museums, and landmarks worldwide through virtual tours, providing immersive experiences without leaving the classroom.
2. **Multimedia Content:** Accessing videos, podcasts, documentaries, and photos online exposes students to diverse cultural perspectives, traditions, and practices.
3. **Interactive Websites:** Utilize interactive websites and apps that offer cultural quizzes, language learning tools, and immersive cultural experiences to engage students actively.
4. **Social Media Analysis:** Analyzing social media platforms allows students to examine how culture is represented, constructed, and negotiated online, fostering discussions on identity, representation, and communication norms.
5. **Online Forums and Communities:** Engaging with online forums and communities related to specific cultures enables students to interact with native speakers, exchange ideas, and gain firsthand insights into cultural practices and perspectives.
6. **Cultural Blogs and Websites:** Encourage students to explore blogs, articles, and websites dedicated to cultural exploration, travel experiences, and cultural exchange to deepen their understanding of diverse cultures.

7. Digital Storytelling: Assignments involving digital storytelling, such as creating multimedia presentations, podcasts, or blogs about cultural topics, empower students to express their cultural insights creatively.

8. Data Analysis: Analyzing data from online sources, such as demographic statistics, cultural surveys, and trend reports, provides empirical insights into cultural dynamics, migration patterns, and societal changes.

By leveraging the internet as a teaching material, educators can enrich cultural education, promote digital literacy, and facilitate cross-cultural understanding among students.

Using pictures, realia (real-life objects), and films in teaching culture is very beneficial for learners. here some basics of them...

VISUAL REPRESENTATION: Pictures, realia, and films provide visual representations of cultural elements, making abstract concepts more concrete and tangible for students.

AUTHENTICITY: Real-life objects and film scenes offer authentic glimpses into cultural artifacts, traditions, and practices, enhancing students' understanding and appreciation of different cultures.

ENGAGEMENT: Visual materials like pictures and films capture students' attention and stimulate their interest in learning about diverse cultures, fostering engagement and active participation in the learning process.

CULTURAL CONTEXT: Films and realia provide contextual information about cultural norms, values, and behaviors, helping students understand cultural practices within their social and historical contexts.

MULTISENSORY LEARNING: Realia allows students to engage multiple senses, facilitating multisensory learning experiences that promote deeper understanding and retention of cultural information.

CULTURAL SENSITIVITY: By incorporating authentic cultural artifacts and film representations, educators can promote cultural sensitivity and respect for diverse cultural perspectives among students.

LANGUAGE ACQUISITION: Films offer opportunities for language immersion and acquisition, allowing students to hear authentic speech patterns, accents, and idiomatic expressions in context.

CRITICAL THINKING: Analyzing visual materials like films and pictures encourages students to critically evaluate representations of culture, identify stereotypes, and consider alternative perspectives.

Overall, the use of pictures, realia, and films in teaching culture enhances the learning experience, fosters cultural empathy, and promotes a deeper understanding of the complexities of human diversity.

Cultural understanding refers to having insight, empathy, and appreciation for the beliefs, values, customs, practices, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. It involves recognizing and respecting the diversity of human experiences, traditions, and worldviews. Cultural understanding goes beyond surface-level knowledge of cultural facts and stereotypes; it entails a deeper comprehension of the historical, social, and contextual factors that shape individuals' identities and behaviors within their cultural contexts. Culturally understanding individuals are open-minded, tolerant, and able to communicate and

interact effectively across cultural boundaries, fostering mutual respect, cooperation, and harmony in diverse multicultural environments.

What is the cultural misunderstanding? Cultural misunderstanding occurs when there is a lack of awareness, misinterpretation, or miscommunication between individuals or groups from different cultural backgrounds. It can arise from differences in beliefs, values, norms, communication styles, gestures, customs, and worldviews. Cultural misunderstandings often stem from assumptions, stereotypes, ethnocentrism, or ignorance about other cultures, leading to unintended offense, confusion, or conflict. Examples include misinterpreting a gesture or expression, misunderstanding the significance of certain customs or rituals, or incorrectly interpreting the tone or intent of communication. Cultural misunderstandings can hinder effective communication, cooperation, and collaboration, and may contribute to interpersonal tensions, prejudice, discrimination, or cultural clashes. Addressing cultural misunderstandings requires cultural sensitivity, empathy, open-mindedness, and a willingness to learn and adapt to diverse cultural perspectives and practices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, selecting appropriate materials for teaching culture is essential for fostering understanding and appreciation among learners. By incorporating diverse and authentic resources, educators can create engaging and enriching learning experiences that promote cultural awareness and sensitivity. Moreover, using a variety of materials allows for a more comprehensive exploration of cultural themes, leading to a deeper understanding of the complexities and nuances inherent in different societies. Ultimately, the careful selection and thoughtful integration of materials can help cultivate global citizens who are equipped to navigate an increasingly interconnected world with empathy and respect for cultural diversity.

References:

1. Hall, E. T. (1976). *Beyond Culture*. Anchor Books.
2. Byram, M. (1997). *Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence*. Multilingual Matters.
3. Kramsch, C. (1993). *Context and Culture in Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
4. Seelye, H. N. (1993). *Teaching Culture: Strategies for Intercultural Communication*. National Textbook Company.
5. Cortazzi, M., & Jin, L. (1999). Cultural Mirrors: Materials and Methods in the EFL Classroom. In *ELT Journal*, 53(2), 136–144.
6. Risager, K. (2007). *Language and Culture Pedagogy: From a National to a Transnational Paradigm*. Multilingual Matters.
7. "O'quv uslubiy majmua"2020. A. Toshmatov - ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasi kafedrası o'qituvchisi